

A comparative analysis of managerial competency needs across areas of functional specialization

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Purpose- The purpose of the study was to investigate whether there is a set of management competencies that should be possessed by managers irrespective of their areas of functional specialization using quantitative methodology.

Design/methodology/approach- For the study, 31 individual competencies were analyzed. The study is confined to a fully integrated telecommunication service provider; 198 managerial employees participated in the survey.

Findings- The findings of the study led to reveal broad level competencies that are important for managers working in one of the seven functional areas. The findings suggested the importance of competencies from value and skill clusters than knowledge cluster across all functional areas. Further, there was hardly any congruent with the perceptions on current expertise and current importance across all the functional areas. Whilst the findings of the study have a specific relevance to the managers in the telecommunication industry, the findings of the study could have a rather broader relevance with implications for management development initiatives.

Originality/value- Though there is an enormous diversity in the scope of competency literature, a few empirical research studies have been conducted on management competency requirements for different functional areas. A limited number of competency studies have been conducted in Asia and in many cases those were confined to identify requisite competencies for managers from a specific functional area, such as HRD. Hence, empirical research studies are needed to fill this lacuna in literature.

Keyword(s): Managerial competencies, competency gaps, competency needs, Sri Lanka.

Paper type: Research paper

Introduction

In a rapidly changing work environment, increased focus on customer and rapid response to problems and opportunities has made the manager a vital resource in guiding and directing front-line workers to success (Hay Group, 2001). The impact of outstanding managers on revenue and profit is well documented. Therefore, in a continuously changing environment, for a sustained personal development, an expansion of a person's capacity to be effective in managerial roles becomes vital (Davis et al., 2004; Jackson et al., 2003; Tubbs and Schulz, 2006). In this regard, the competency approach marks a new development and the importance given to competencies in the organizational context is continually increasing (Matthewman, 1995).

Competency frameworks are commonly used at the organizational level to guide decision-making; Lawler (1994) writes: “competency-based organizations are organizational systems in which the capabilities of individuals are the primary focus, which cause them to be managed in a way that provides competitive advantage” (p.6). Vertically, competency framework is a tool to delineate individual and organizational competencies from the mission and strategy of the organization. Horizontally, competency framework can be used for different purposes in human resource management (HRM) including selection, management development, career and succession planning, and performance management (Rothwell and Lindholm, 1999; Schippmann et al., 2000). Therefore, competencies are the common language, which enable an organization to match its human resources against the resources it needs (Antonacopoulou and FitzGerald 1996; Harvey et al., 2000).

When capturing and capitalizing on individual capabilities, it is important to understand whether managers working in different work environments require different sets of competencies in order to satisfy the different job demands that encounter or whether different

job demands connected to different areas of functional specialization could be satisfied by a common set of management competencies. Though there is an enormous diversity in the scope of competency studies, a few empirical research studies have been conducted on management competency requirements for different functional areas. Findings of such studies have indicated that the variations in functions and contexts of managerial roles make a one-size-fits-all competency profile impractical (Barber and Tietje, 2004; Hayes et al., 2000; McKenna, 2002). The identification of competencies that match job requirements has become an issue in human resource development (HRD) in any context.

In many instances, a vague list of desirable competencies provided by policymakers or advocated by scholars is used as a guide in making crucial decisions on HRD programmes. Further, several academic literature propose that competency needs should be identified in terms of gaps as a gap informs whether there is a deficiency in a competency while reducing managers' subjectivity and preference in identifying managerial competency needs. However, a few empirical studies have been conducted treating competency needs as gaps (Agut et al., 2003; Barber and Tietje, 2004; Chen et al., 2005; Hansson, 2001). Finally, a limited number of competency studies have been conducted in Asia and in many cases those were confined to identify requisite competencies for managers from a specific functional area, such as HRD (see- Chen et al., 2005; Han et al., 2006; Zhu et al., 2000). Therefore, this research aims to partially fill this lacuna in literature by investigating whether there is a set of management competencies that should be possessed irrespective of the functional area to which they are attached to using quantitative methodology.

For the study, following research questions were raised: 1. What are the current competency expertise levels across the areas of functional specialization? 2. What competencies are perceived to be important for now and near future by the managers across the areas of functional specialization? 3. Are there any differences among current competency expertise, current importance, and future importance? If so, what are current and future competency needs in terms of gaps across the areas of functional specialization? Based on these three

research questions the following specific research objectives were developed: 1. to investigate managers' perceived competency levels across the areas of functional specialization, 2. to evaluate the perceived importance of competencies for now and near future across the areas of functional specialization, and 3. to analyze current and future competency needs across the areas of functional specialization.

The perceived levels of current expertise, current importance, and future importance of 31 different individual work-related competencies were measured across three competency clusters- knowledge, skill and value across seven functional areas. Hence, the procedure adopted in this research not only allows the possibility of modelling competencies differently but it also generates data that can be used to contrast the individual estimates. In order to provide the context for the paper, the next section briefly reviews the theoretical background of the study. This is followed by the methodology adopted. Subsequently, the main findings are presented and discussed. The paper concludes with a discussion on the implications of the findings and research areas for further inquiry and understanding.

Theoretical background

In this section theoretical background related to the concepts of “competency”, “competency gaps”, and “measurement issues with the competency approach” are discussed.

Competency

The term “competency” was first used in the managerial context in the research conducted by Boyatzis (1982) in the late 1970s in the USA to identify the characteristics which distinguish superior from average managerial performance. Boyatzis adopted the term “competency”, plural “competencies”, which he described as an underlying characteristic of an individual that is causally related to effective or superior performance in a job (Boyatzis, 1982). The study concluded that there was no single factor but a range of factors that differentiated superior

from average performers. These included personal characteristics, experience, motives and other attributes. Following the definition given by Hay Group (2001), for this study a competency is considered as a measurable characteristic of a person that is related to effective performance in a specific job, organization or culture. These characteristics are defined in terms of behaviors. Because competencies are behavioral, they can be developed.

Competency gaps

It is important to identify which particular set of key individual competencies are required for a business to achieve its strategic goals. Antonacopoulou and FitzGerald (1996) state that there is a danger if organizations concentrate on competencies of the past rather than on competencies of tomorrow. Hence, competency framework should reflect an organization's current and future needs (Prahalad and Hamel, 1990). In this regard, competency management has an important contribution at the organizational and individual levels as it ensures that individual competencies are linked to strategies of an organization (Draganidis and Mentzas, 2006; Homer, 2001). Equally vital is the ability to "health-check" those competencies on a regular basis (Homer, 2001). Hence, from the management development viewpoint, it is important to know whether managers possess the required competencies to achieve an expert job performance. In this context, literature suggests that when competency needs are considered in terms of gaps, it allows for a better understanding of managerial performance (Agut et al., 2003; Barber and Tietje, 2004; Scholes and Endacott, 2003).

A discrepancy or a gap arises when a competency an individual possesses is lower than what is required for the expert job performance (Agut and Grau, 2002; Boydell and Leary, 1996; Goldstein, 1991). Further, there are differences in the importance of different competencies for performing a job. By taking into account individuals' perceptions of how important a specific competency is for performing a particular job could avoid an unbalanced focus on less important competencies (Hansson, 2001). Though a perceived gap could sometimes be an expression of preference (Latham, 1988), such information is useful in

decision making. For instance, once competency gaps were identified and, if necessary, an organization could decide to address those through appropriate strategies such as training, job enrichment, job content innovation, job redesign, enhancement of the organizational climate, etc. (Goldstein, 1991; Naquin and Holton, 2003; Tharenou, 1991; Wright and Geroy, 1992).

Measurement issues with the competency approach

Though popularity of competency frameworks among practitioners increasing, scientific community has regarded competency studies with some degree of scepticism (Lievens et al., 2004). The validity of “competencies” as measurable constructs appears to be at the core of this controversy (Lawler, 1996; Schippmann et al., 2000; Tett et al., 2000). Content validity means that the list of competencies used for the study is a representative sample of the universe of interest. Face validity means that the competencies are accurate and appropriate as judged by their users. In this regard, Hayes et al. (2000) argue that the lists of competencies will always be incomplete. They cite examples of studies where managers have not been able to describe all the competencies required for a job. Construct validity emphasizes the importance of operationalizing competencies so as to observe and measure (Markus et al., 2005).

In criterion validity, the importance of measuring competencies accurately is emphasized. However, the way competencies are operationalized and measure depend on how those will be used. Competencies are usually assessed using three distinct methodologies: self-evaluation that allows the assessment of the improvement and/or decline of competencies over time; third-party evaluation that allows the monitoring and evaluation of the evolution of individual learning/acquisition of competencies; peer evaluation that allows the evaluation of the possession of competencies as perceived by peers (Camuffo and Gerli, 2004; Graham and Tarbell, 2006). However, the assessment of competencies is likely to

suffer from reliability problems, such as rater bias (Fletcher, 2001). Therefore, an accurate measurement of competencies is a key issue (Markus et al., 2005).

The empirical study- case company

The study is confined to a fully integrated telecommunication service provider, identified as X Company. It has become the leading company in the industry in Sri Lanka. According to the monthly human resource report as at July 2006, X Company has more than 6,000 employees in total. Specifically, there were 541 managerial level employees, 1026 middle level technical employees, 1279 clerical and aligned employees, 605 call centre employees, 2,232 technical employees, 358 non-technical employees and 290 drivers as the total number of permanent employees. Of the total employees (6331), 2484 attached to headquarter while 3847 attached to regional offices island wide. Average age of the employees is 42.

Managerial level employees of X Company were considered as the population of the study. Of the 541 managerial level employees, 510 were contactable during September 2006 when the survey was conducted. The questionnaire was distributed through e-mail and printed form; it was voluntarily completed and returned by 203 subjects within 4 weeks of initial questionnaire distribution. A total of 198 usable responses resulted in a 39 per cent response rate. The final sample covered all the fields of employment as shown in Table 1. Of the 198 respondents, 70 per cent were males and 30 per cent were females. The mean age was 40 years; 85 per cent married while 15 per cent single. Of the sample, 85 per cent reported having a Bachelors or postgraduate level university education. The current job tenure in X Company was 13 years on average while the current job tenure in X Company in the current field of specialization was 7 years on average. On average, there were 9 subordinates directly reporting each respondent.

Insert Table 1 about here

Method

In this section, measures used in the study, data collection procedures adopted and the methods of data analysis are presented.

Measures

To achieve the purpose of the study, the identification of individual competencies formed the foundation. In generating the list of competencies to be considered for the research, the methodologies adopted by recent competency research were studied. The literature offer different and often overlapping taxonomies of managerial competencies (see- Agut et al., 2003; Hackett, 2001; Tubbs and Schulz, 2006; Yang et al., 2006). The current study has more developmental focus; educational objectives are often categorized into three distinct domains – cognitive, affective and psychomotor (see- Barber and Tietje, 2004). Therefore, following the work of Barber and Tietje (2004), for the current study, knowledge-skill-value (KSV) structure was used. The term knowledge was used to represent the cognitive domain, value for the affective, and skill for the psychomotor.

In the current study, five-step methodology was adopted to identify competencies that define a successful manager. First, a comprehensive list of competencies was created that were taken from competency literature. Second, in order to standardize the terminology of competency items, a list of 107 competencies was summarised that are abstracted from various sources in literature. This list was considered as the hypothesized list of competencies. This list was independently analyzed by the two researchers and classified into the competency clusters of knowledge-skill-value. As the third step, a panel of industry

experts from the telecommunication industry was consulted to rank the importance of each competency for managers in the telecommunication industry from the hypothesized competency list created. To ensure the competencies that are going to be required of managers are valid and useful, as the forth step, a randomly selected team of managers from the telecommunication industry was consulted to rank the importance of each competency for managers in the telecommunication industry from the hypothesized competency list created. It was decided to take the competencies that are consistently rated of great importance by the two panels. Therefore, as the final step, the initial list along with the ranks given by the two panels were independently analysed by the two researchers to identify the most important competencies and to eliminate duplicates. The final list comprised 31 individual competencies (8 knowledge, 13 skill, and 10 value) and reflected the absolute minimum number of areas in which capabilities are required for an expert performance in a job (refer- Table 2).

Procedure

Self-evaluation method of personal competencies was used in the research as it plays an increasingly prominent role in education and training field (see- Camuffo and Gerli, 2004; Hansson, 2001; Kersh and Evans, 2005; Tovey, 1994, 2006). The design of the research is such that an individual performs three estimations (current expertise, current importance, and future importance) on the instrument on 31 different individual work-related competencies. In the current expertise, a respondent estimates his/her competence on each item. In current importance, a respondent makes a judgment on how important a particular competency in performing his/her job now. In future importance, a respondent makes a judgment on how important a particular competency for the future job performance (three years to the future). The self-administered survey questionnaire employed a five point Likert type scale to establish three competency levels (current expertise- 5=Very High, 4=High, 3=Average, 2=Low, 1=Nothing at all; current importance and future importance- 5=Very High, 4=High,

3=Average, 2=Low, 1=No Need). Cronbach's alpha reliabilities for each of the three competency clusters were above the customary reference point of 0.70 (refer-Table 2).

In the research, two competency gaps were established- current and future. The current gap (need) was established by measuring the difference between the level of perceived current competency expertise and current importance. The future need was established by measuring the difference between the level of perceived current importance and future importance (see- Agut et al., 2003; Hansson, 2001; Tovey, 1994). The two gaps were calculated for each respondent for each competency item. Following the criterion proposed by Agut and Grau (2002) and Agut et al. (2003), three types of competency gaps were identified: negative gap (the present competency level is lower than that required: value \leq -.51); adjustment margin (the present competency level is lower but close to that required: $-.50 \leq$ value \leq .5); and positive gap (the present competency level is higher than that required: value \geq .51).

The self-administrated survey questionnaire was pre-tested prior to the distribution. The questionnaire's format, length, style, wording and potential duplication were assessed during the pre-test. The pre-tested survey questionnaire after amendments was administered among the respondents as detailed in the section on "the empirical study".

Methods of data analysis

Data analysis was carried out by using the software package for social sciences (SPSS). Descriptive statistics were used to analyze scores of current expertise, current importance, and future importance and also to derive gaps. One way analysis of variance (ANOVA) and post hoc tests (Least Significant Differences) were used to determine whether there are significant differences across functional areas.

Results

Table 3 summarizes the results for the highest expertise areas and the most important competencies for now and future across functional areas. As that can be seen in Table 3, different functional areas emphasize different competencies as important for current and in future.

Insert Table 3 about here

Table 4 summarizes the results for the significant differences in competency levels across seven functional areas. The results indicated that current expertise level of 9 competencies have significant differences across functional areas. When it comes to current importance, three competencies showed significant differences across functional areas. With regard to future importance, seven competencies showed significant differences across functional areas. Overall, major perception differences existed in the legal group with compared to other six categories including IT, Finance, etc. For the rest of the competencies investigated, the perceived competency levels were consistent across the respondent groups.

Insert Table 4 about here

Table 5 summarizes the results for the most needed competencies (with highest gaps) for now and future across functional areas. As that can be seen in Table 5, different competencies are rated as the most needed for now and the future across functional areas.

Insert Table 5 about here

Table 6 summarizes the results for the significant differences in current and future competency needs across three competency clusters (knowledge, skill and value) across seven functional areas. It was assumed that gaps represent the need for competencies. Therefore, the larger the mean difference, the more the competency would be needed. Though all most all competency gaps revealed either negative gap or adjustment margin, all the mean values were not statistically significant. Current competency needs for two competencies showed significant differences across functional areas while future competency needs for four competencies showed significant differences across functional areas. For the rest of the competencies investigated, the competency gaps were all most consistent across the respondent groups.

Insert Table 6 about here

Concluding remarks and implications

The study made an attempt to elicit competency requirements of managers working in different parts of the same organization that they thought were necessary for effective performance. The findings of the study led to reveal broad level competencies that are important for managers working in one of the seven functional areas. The findings suggested the importance of competencies from value and skill clusters than knowledge cluster across all functional areas. Further, in majority of the situations, there was hardly any congruent with the perceptions on current expertise and current importance across all the functional areas. Furthermore, managers perceived that technical competencies will be important in the future across all functional areas. This implies their awareness that they are expected to possess

competencies associated with emerging technology, especially when attached to telecommunication industry. However, major perception differences could be found in the legal area when compared to the other areas of functional specialization. Though the respondents of the study were limited to telecommunication sector the most of the competencies investigated appear to be more useful across managerial domains. Therefore, whilst the findings of the study have a specific relevance to the managers in the telecommunication industry, the findings of the study could have a rather broader relevance. This study has several implications for management development initiatives.

The study is based on an operative method to analyze competency needs in terms of gaps, as the academic literature proposes. As long as competency deficits are accurately detected, those could be addressed through the most appropriate strategy. However, academic literature very often recognizes the integration of competency management with learning management systems (see- Bartram, 2004; Hackett, 2001; Homer, 2001; Mumford et al., 2000; Naquin and Holton, 2003; Reio and Sutton, 2006). Though this could be criticized because a deficit in competency does not necessarily imply an adoption of a management development solution, the link between competencies and management development interventions add tremendous value to users who can immediately see what interventions that they need in order to acquire competencies. Therefore, competency based interventions is seen as an important strategic tool in addressing competency gaps (see –McClelland, 1994; Jackson et al., 2003). In this research we also consider that to face a continuously changing environment managers' competencies need to be renewed on a regular basis. Therefore, management development interventions could play a major role in expanding a person's capacity to be effective in managerial roles and processes.

However, the findings of the study imply the management development challenges in incorporating a proper balance of knowledge, skill and value competencies into managerial competency development programmes. In this regard, once competency gaps have been identified, organizations have to decide whether there is a real need of addressing each and every competency gap; what would be the cost of ignoring a competency gap? In making such critical decisions, competency management has an important contribution as it ensures that individual competencies are linked to strategies of the organization. Here, the key integrative concept is that of occupational competence, especially managerial competence. Therefore, the identification of the set of individual competencies and competency gaps in terms of an organization's specific business strategies across the functional areas of specialization would be the most important.

Having diagnosed the most important competencies, it is then necessary to target and develop them continuously and improvements must be measured. Hence, on one hand, this recognizes the importance of ensuring that the individual development plans are linked to business goals. On the other hand this recognizes the need of having performance measurement systems which are as objective and robust as possible. However, business pressures and uncertainty create needs for new competencies suggesting that organizations have to develop or acquire new competencies. Hence, there is a need of refining the lists of competencies continuously.

In the organizational context where resources are scarce, an organization could also create a culture where individuals maintain their own personal competency profile along with their personal development plan. Individual managers can identify the most important competencies for the present and the future, and then use this information to design, develop and evaluate their jobs and roles. The outcome of this effort would be beneficial for both the individual and organization in designing careers and satisfying individual aspirations.

The literature gives evidence to growing tendency towards decentralisation and a concomitant shift towards greater devolvement of responsibility to line management in the areas traditionally held to be the domain of HR specialists. Competency management is no exception. Line managers engage in selection, assessment, development and succession of individual employees under his/her supervision. All these four activities are influenced by competencies. Therefore, line managers have to ensure that individual competency requirements remain strategically focused. HR managers have to evaluate the competencies on a regular basis to become strategic and flexible and to support required organizational changes. This implies that when competitive advantage is largely based on competencies, organizations have to redefine the role of line managers and HR managers to meet the expectations of them. This leads back to the competency requirements of HR managers and line managers of other functional areas.

Overall, the judicious management of competencies shows an orientation towards the future and could adopt a multiple constituency perspective, where, first, from individuals' standpoint, they have the possibility to develop a set of competencies that could be helpful in advancing in their careers. Second, from an organization's standpoint, the identification of competencies could help align HR system vertically with the organization's strategic objectives by capturing and capitalizing on individual capabilities. It could also help align the HR system horizontally with other HR functions, where the results of the study provide a decision-making tool for several HR functions such as management of careers. Third, from management development professionals' standpoint, they could identify sound methodologies to address competency needs based on employer expectations.

Limitations and further research

For the study purposes competencies were defined simply, as a headline plus a few sample behaviours; competency definitions used do not cater for multiple levels of detail and mastery. Therefore, though it was found that some competencies are equally needed for several functional areas, findings could be interpreted as there may be similarities at higher levels of abstraction but there may be differences at the level of detail. Further, the study relied on self-reporting method to assess competency levels. However, there could be situations where individuals consistently give higher (or lower) estimates of the importance of the items as well as higher (or lower) estimates of their own competency. Hence, future studies could also collect data from multiple sources, such as subordinates and peers. Furthermore, future studies could use qualitative data to obtain in-depth understanding. The future studies could also be conducted through a larger sample across an industry, rather than confine to a single organization.

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Tables

Table 1: Population and sample

Functional area	Population	Sample	% represented in the sample
Finance	38	17	45
IT	32	12	38
Marketing	86	28	33
HR & Administration	76	28	37
Legal	10	7	70
Planning & Corporate Strategy	33	18	55
Operations	235	88	37
Total	510	198	39

Table 2: Competencies and Cronbach's standardized item alpha values

Competencies	Current expertise	Current importance	Future importance
Knowledge: 1. Customer relations knowledge 2. Cost consciousness 3. Change handling skills 4. Planning and scheduling 5. Strategizing ability 6. Technical competence 7. Technology management 8. Safety focus	.8318	.8392	.8825
Skill: 9. Empathy with people 10. Conflict resolution 11. Negotiation 12. Empowerment 13. Holistic 14. Creativity 15. Coaching ability 16. Time management 17. Pressure management skills 18. Learning 19. Listening 20. Oral communication 21. Written communication	.8965	.9290	.9411
Value: 22. Quality focus 23. Flexibility 24. Team player 25. Customer focus 26. Resiliency 27. Ethical 28. Achievement orientation 29. Risk taking 30. Positive vision 31. Attitude to meet targets	.8871	.8973	.9265

Table 3: Summary of results for current expertise, current importance and future importance across functional areas

Area	1 st rank*	2 nd rank*	3 rd rank*
Finance			
Current expertise:	Resiliency	Listening	Team player
Current importance:	Oral communication	Resiliency	Pressure management skills
Future importance:	Written communication, Quality focus	Pressure management skills, Listening	Resiliency
IT			
Current expertise:	Flexibility	Achievement orientation	Empathy with people
Current importance:	Achievement orientation	Pressure management skills	Creativity
Future importance:	Time management	Achievement orientation	Customer focus
Marketing			
Current expertise:	Attitude to meet targets	Team player	Flexibility
Current importance:	Team player, Customer focus	Written communication, Quality focus, Flexibility	Customer relations knowledge
Future importance:	Time management, Customer focus	Attitude to meet targets	Written communication
HRM			
Current expertise:	Flexibility	Team player	Listening
Current importance:	Time management, Written communication	Team player	Oral communication
Future importance:	Change handling skills	Technology management	Attitude to meet targets
Legal			
Current expertise:	Listening	Planning and scheduling	Written communication, Ethical
Current importance:	Resiliency	Quality focus	Team player
Future importance:	Negotiation	Team player, Attitude to meet targets	Technical competence, Learning, Resiliency
Planning			
Current expertise:	Positive vision	Attitude to meet targets	Time management
Current importance:	Positive vision, Attitude to meet targets	Achievement orientation, Quality focus	Pressure management skills, Negotiation
Future importance:	Technical competence	Team player, Achievement orientation	Creativity, Positive vision
Operations			
Current expertise:	Attitude to meet targets	Empathy with people	Team player
Current importance:	Planning and scheduling	Attitude to meet targets	Team player
Future importance:	Customer relations knowledge	Attitude to meet targets	Technical competence

Note: * Ranks are based on mean values

Table 4: Summary of results for the significant differences in current expertise, current importance and future importance across functional areas

Competency	Total sample (Mean)	Functional area (Mean)							Sig
		Finance	IT	Marketing	HRM	Legal	Planning	Operations	
Current expertise									
Knowledge :									
6. Technical competence	3.73	3.65	4.08 AFG	3.52 ABE	3.26 CDF	3.20 GH	4.00 BCH	3.92 DE	.001
7. Technology management	3.67	3.71 A	4.00 B	3.75 C	3.26 ACD	2.71 ABCEF	3.89 DE	3.77 DF	.001
8. Safety focus	3.84	3.65	3.50 A	3.89	3.57 B	3.29 C	4.00	4.03 ABC	.038
Skill:									
14. Innovative/Creativity	3.76	3.56	4.08 AH	3.75 BF	3.33 ABCG	3.00 DEFH	4.06 CD	3.89 EG	.001
16. Time Management	3.89	4.06 A	3.83 B	4.14 C	3.54 ACD	3.00 ABCEF	4.28 DE	3.90 DF	.001
17. Pressure management skill	3.75	3.75	3.67	3.44 AC	3.43 BD	3.43	4.00 AB	3.95 CD	.007
Value:									
25. Customer focus	3.91	3.65	3.75	4.14 A	3.74	3.00 ABC	4.06 B	4.01 C	.033
28. Achievement orientation	3.88	3.59 AG	4.27 AB	3.93 C	3.70 D	3.14 BCEF	4.28 DEG	3.89 F	.014
29. Risk taking	3.80	3.94 A	3.67 B	3.71 C	3.68 D	2.86 ABCDEF	4.06 E	3.88 F	.034
Current importance									
Knowledge:									
1. Customer relations knowledge	4.05	3.82 A	3.83 B	4.60 ABCD	4.18 EF	3.14 CEH	3.39 DFG	4.15 GH	.003
6. Technical competence	4.23	4.12 A	4.33	4.33	3.89 B	3.60 C	4.72 ABCD	4.24 D	.040
Value:									
25. Customer focus	4.06	3.65 A	3.67 B	4.68 ABCDE	4.22	3.67 C	3.88 D	4.03 E	.015
Future importance									
Knowledge:									
1. Customer relations knowledge	4.62	4.50 A	4.42 B	4.76 C	4.79 D	3.71 ABCDEF	4.56 E	4.66 F	.020
3. Change handling skills	4.54	4.50	4.17 ABC	4.68 A	4.86 D	4.20	4.72 C	4.42 D	.043
7. Technology management	4.54	4.44 A	4.75 B	4.64 C	4.85 DE	3.71 ABCDFG	4.44 F	4.47 EG	.036
Skill:									
14. Creativity	4.57	4.67 A	4.67 B	4.64 C	4.70 D	3.71 ABCDEF	4.78 E	4.49 F	.018
16. Time Management	4.63	4.60 A	4.92 B	4.92 CD	4.79 E	3.43 ABCEFG	4.67 F	4.53 DG	.000
Value:									
25. Customer focus	4.56	3.94 ABCDE	4.75 AF	4.92 BGH	4.64 CI	3.80 FGIJK	4.76 DJ	4.51 EHK	.001
28. Achievement orientation	4.63	4.44	4.91 A	4.72 B	4.81 C	4.14 ABCD	4.83 D	4.53	.027

Notes: The means followed by the same letter are significantly different from each other.
 Values of the standard deviation ranged between .37 (lowest) to 1.12 (highest).

Table 5: Summary of results for the most needed competencies for now and future across functional areas

	1 st rank*	2 nd rank*	3 rd rank*
Finance			
Current need:	Creativity	Coaching ability	Technical competence, Technology management
Future need:	Customer relations knowledge	Conflict resolution	Technical competence
IT			
Current need:	Pressure management skills	Oral communication	Planning and scheduling
Future need:	Time management	Technology management	Cost consciousness
Marketing			
Current need:	Technical competence	Pressure management skills, Quality focus	Negotiation
Future need:	Strategizing ability	Technical competence	Time management
HRM			
Current need:	Pressure management skills, Creativity	Oral communication	Change handling skills
Future need:	Technical competence	Customer relations knowledge, Cost consciousness	Customer focus
Legal			
Current need:	Holistic, Time management	Quality focus, Achievement orientation	Oral communication
Future need:	Technical competence	Customer relations knowledge, Safety focus, Time management	Technology management
Planning			
Current need:	Technical competence	Pressure management skills, Quality focus	Change handling skills
Future need:	Customer relations knowledge	Customer focus	Flexibility
Operations			
Current need:	Oral communication	Achievement orientation, Time management	Planning and scheduling
Future need:	Technology management	Customer relations knowledge	Customer focus

Note: * Ranks are based on gaps

Table 6: Summary of results for the significant differences in current and future competency needs across functional areas

Competency	Total sample		Area of specialization														Sig
			Finance		IT		Marketing		HRM		Legal		Planning		Operations		
	Mean	Gap	Mean	Gap	Mean	Gap	Mean	Gap	Mean	Gap	Mean	Gap	Mean	Gap	Mean	Gap	
Current need																	
Skill:																	
16. Time Management	-0.50	AM	-0.18 A	AM	-0.16 B	AM	-0.40 E	AM	-1.07 ABCDE	N	-1.00	N	-0.16 C	AM	-0.47 D	AM	.022
17. Pressure Management skill	-0.53	N	-0.56	N	-0.83	N	-0.83 A	N	-0.96 B	N	-0.50	AM	-0.44	AM	-0.24 AB	AM	.017
Future need																	
Knowledge:																	
1. Customer relations knowledge	-0.57	N	-0.68	N	-0.58	N	-0.16 A	AM	-0.60 B	N	-0.57	N	-1.16 ABC	N	-0.52 C	N	.026
Skill:																	
16. Time Management	-0.23	AM	-0.33 AB	AM	-0.91 ACFGIK	N	-0.40 CD	AM	-0.17 EF	AM	.57 BDFHJK	N	-0.22 GH	AM	-0.13 IJ	AM	.001
Value:																	
23. Flexibility	-0.22	AM	-0.31	AM	-0.41	AM	-0.12 A	AM	-0.39 B	AM	.00 C	AM	-0.66 ACD	N	-0.06 BD	AM	.040
27. Ethical	-0.23	AM	-0.37 A	AM	-0.58 BC	N	.10 B	AM	-0.40 D	AM	.57 ACDEF	N	-0.33 E	AM	-0.21 F	AM	.027

Notes:

Nature of Gap: Value \leq -.51: negative gap (N), $-.50 \leq$ Value \leq .5: adjustment margin (AM), Value \geq .51: positive gap (P)

The means followed by the same letter are significantly different from each other.

Values of the standard deviation ranged between .42 (lowest) to 1.14 (highest).